

GenAI & Security Trainings

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* Required

1. How many years of professional coding experience do you have? *

- <1
- 1-3
- 4-6
- 7-10
- >10

2. How often do you use LLMs or generative AI tools in your coding or security-related tasks? *

- Frequently
- Rarely
- Never
- Occasionally
- Always

3. To what extent do you agree with the statement: "Using LLMs enhances my ability to identify vulnerabilities in code." *

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

4. How likely are you to incorporate LLM-assisted code reviews into your future projects? *

- Very likely
- Somewhat likely
- Neither likely nor unlikely
- Somewhat unlikely
- Very unlikely

5. How would you rate the quality of feedback provided by the LLM compared to your manual review? *

- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Fair

Very good

6. Do you agree that the multi-step process of ASCEND (manual review, LLM analysis, re-analysis, and code correction) is beneficial for learning secure coding practices? *

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly disagree

7. On average, how much time did you spend reviewing each code snippet using the ASCEND platform? *

Less than 5 minutes

5-10 minutes

More than 10 minutes

8. How confident are you in identifying all the vulnerabilities in the code snippets on the platform? *

Very confident

Somewhat confident

Neutral

Somewhat not confident

Not confident at all

9. To what extent do you agree with the statement: "LLM-assisted secure code reviews help reduce human error in identifying vulnerabilities." *

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly disagree

10. Overall, how satisfied are you with the ASCEND secure code review platform? *

11. Which additional features would you like to see in an LLM-assisted secure code review tool? *

Code Diff

Terminal Access

Other

12. How much do you trust LLMs to provide accurate secure code analysis? *

Do not trust them at all

I'm not sure

Some what trust them

- Trust but verify
- Trust completely

13. Have you encountered any issues or limitations when using LLMs for coding? *

Enter your answer

14. To what extent do you agree with the statement: "Using generative AI for software development increases my overall productivity" *

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

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